

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART XIV. SOME NEW N⁴-HETEROCYCLIC ACYL-SULPHANILAMIDES*

BY B. C. JAIN, B. H. IYER AND P. C. GUHA

Fourteen N⁴-heterocyclic acyl-sulphanilamides are described.

Although according to Fourneau *et al.* (*Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1936, 122, 258) the therapeutic activity of sulphanilamide is greatly reduced by the introduction of an acyl group at N⁴-position, the fact that N⁴-substituted sulphanilamides like N⁴-furoyl sulphapyridine (Kolloff and Hunter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1646), N⁴-nicotiny sulphanilamide (Daniels and Iwamoto, *ibid.*, 1940, 62, 741), N⁴-quinoyl sulphanilamide (Hykes *et al.*, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1937, 126, 635) and N⁴-2-pyrrolidone-5'-carboxy-4-aminobenzene sulphanilamide (Gray *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 724) have been reported to possess high therapeutic activity, would warrant further studies in this direction. It was therefore thought of interest to make a systematic study of the effect of heterocyclic diacyl substituents at the N⁴-position of the sulphanilamide molecule.

The present paper details the preparation and properties of fourteen N⁴-heterocyclic acyl-sulphanilamides obtained from the following heterocyclic acids, esters or anhydrides: (a) quinolinic acid (*cf.* Jain *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1945, 8, 59), (b) diethylidihydrocollidine dicarboxylate, (c) collidine dicarboxylic acid, (d) chelidamic acid, (e) furan-2 : 5-dicarboxylic acid, (f) diethyl 3 : 4-dihydroxyfuran-2 : 5-dicarboxylate (Guha and Iyer, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1938, 21A, 115), (g) diethyl furo-3 : 4-p-2 : 5-dicarboxylate, (h) cantharidin, (i) diethyl 3 : 4-dihydroxythiophen-2 : 5-dicarboxylate, (j) diethyl thieno-3 : 4-p-dioxan-2 : 5-dicarboxylate, and (k) diethyl diacetosuccinate.

* *cf.* Jain *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1945-46, 11, 270.

Quinolinic anhydride reacts with sulphanilamide to give pyridine-2-carboxy-3-carbo-N⁴-sulphanilamide (I) which, when heated at 200-210°, eliminates CO₂ giving N⁴-nicotiny sulphanilamide (II) showing that the COOH- in the 2 position of compound (I) is free.

Fusion of (c), (d) and (h) gives collidine-3 : 5-dicarbo- N^4 -disulphanilamide (XI), pyridon-2 : 6-dicarbo- N^4 -disulphanilamide (XII) and 1 : 4-endoxy-cyclohexane-2 : 3-dimethyl-2 : 3-dicarbo- N^4 -sulphanilamide (XIII), respectively.

Action of (h) on sulphanilamide in acetic acid gives 2 : 5-dimethyl-3 : 4-dicarbethoxypyrrole- N -*p*-benzene sulphonamide (XIV). Further condensation of sulphanilamide with the two carbethoxy groups of (XIV) could not be effected under any condition. Similarly diethyl 2 : 3-dimethylpyrrole-2 : 4-dicarboxylate and diethyl 2 : 4-dimethylpyrrole-3 : 5-dicarboxylate did not also react with sulphanilamide indicating the inert nature of the carbethoxy groups.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All the compounds and their analytical data are tabulated below. Most of them being insoluble in common organic solvent were purified by dissolution in 10% alkali and precipitation with dilute hydrochloric acid.

Compounds (I) and (XIV) were prepared by refluxing the solution of the reactants in alcohol and glacial acetic acid respectively, while (II), (III), (IV), (VII), (VIII) and (XIII) were prepared by heating the reactants at suitable temperatures at ordinary pressure ; (V), (IX), (X), (XI) and (XII) were prepared by heating the components at reduced pressure. Two typical experiments are detailed below.

Pyridine-2 : 3-dicarbo- N^4 -disulphanilamide (IV).— To sulphanilamide (3.5 g.), taken in a flask fitted with an air condenser, protected by a calcium chloride tube, quinolinyl chloride (2.5 g.) was added dropwise with shaking and cooling. After 1 hour's keeping at room temperature, it was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour until evolution of HCl ceased. Dry benzene (15 c. c.) was added and after refluxing for 5 minutes, it was filtered hot and the product purified, *m. p.* 293° (decomp.), yield 2.4 g.

Dihydrocollidine-3 : 5-dicarbo-N⁴-disulphanilamide (V).— Sulphanilamide (3.42 g.) and diethyl dihydrocollidine dicarboxylate (2.67 g.) were heated in an oil-bath under reduced pressure (200 mm.) at 150-160° for 2 hours, and then at 200-210° for 1 hour. At the end of the period the molten mass resolidified indicating the completion of the reaction. This was purified as usual, yield 2.6 g., m. p. 285° (decomp.).

TABLE I

No.	Formula.	M.p. (a)	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
I.	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S (e)	210° (b)	13.19	13.08	10.27	9.87
II.	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	257	11.40	11.55	—	—
III.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	311	13.80	13.86	10.90	10.56
IV.	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	293	14.54	14.73	13.01	13.47
V.	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	285	13.43	13.49	11.90	12.33
VI.	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	290	13.40	13.54	12.70	12.37
VII.	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	322	14.13	14.26	12.82	13.03
VIII.	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	255	12.00	12.07	13.43	13.80
IX.	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	260	11.44	11.30	13.25	12.90
X.	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	275	10.84	10.72	12.01	12.28
XI.	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S.	(d)	10.84	10.94	13.10	13.75
XII.	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S.	(d)	10.51	10.40	13.50	17.84
XIII.	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	234	8.24	8.00	9.40	9.14
XIV.	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	204	7.20	7.10	6.40	6.12

(a) Most of the compounds melted with decomposition.

(b) Solidified when kept at 210° for some time and remelted at 257-80°.

(e) Equivalent : Found, 317.4 ; calc., 321.

(d) Decomposed.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
DEPT. OF PURE & APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BANGALORE.

Received September 6, 1946.